

IMPLICATIONS OF AN UNBIASED ASSESMENT IN LITERATURE CLASSES

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Abstract: In this article, problems of student assessment in literary education were studied. The factors such as: age and physiological characteristics of pupils, and schoolbooks compliance with modern requirements and methodological criteria were taken into account in the research process. It had been scientifically and methodologically proven that working on questions and assignments designed for a work of art included in the textbooks had great potential in teaching students to think independently. Experimental work and research results serve as a unique methodological resource in the creation of a new generation of "Literature" textbooks.

Key words: assessment, literature classes, "Literature" textbooks, comparative analysis, interactive assignments, literary-theoretical rules, methodological criteria, pedagogical process.

Introduction.

Today, the student reads whatever is asked on the assessment. Because the marking is everything for the student. However, it is a very difficult process to determine and evaluate the student's knowledge in literature classes, which are included in the arts. That is, it is different from the exact sciences. Disadvantages of the traditional assessment system is that it is aimed at improving the student's knowledge, encouraging them to study, working on themselves and correcting their mistakes, rather than emphasizing their current level and showing their shortcomings once again. In addition, it is not logical to use the same tasks to evaluate students with different levels

of information reception, assimilation and demonstration of their knowledge, as shown in the following picture:

Literature analysis and methodology.

English scientist Joe Kirby, who studied methodological criteria for evaluating student knowledge in the educational system (1, 2015), recommends another method of indicating the level of mastery in his research and explains today's trends with the following picture:

This is more effective to show the student's achievements and shortcomings, which will increase his self-confidence, create a foundation for active, independent and creative work rather than evaluating.

The scientific-pedagogical principles related to the change of the assessment system include the radical renewal of the self-monitoring methods, the PBL (Project-Based Learning) strategy, which has been put into practice today in advanced foreign higher education institutions, and Bloom's taxonomy, which does not recognize the boundaries of the class hour, audience, and subject. requires redesign based on dynamic learning criteria.

Results.

Literature textbooks have a great role in student assessment. students are evaluated by completing the questions for the analysis of the works which given in the textbook. In order to determine the role of "Literature" textbooks in the process of teaching and learning literary material, experimental work was carried out among students in grades 7-9 of secondary schools.

The development of this study is based on a series of pilot surveys conducted among students and teachers of secondary schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Previously, we managed to find out that, in general, there is a need for a wider application of modern interactive teaching methods, at the same time there is a demand for an increase in teaching materials in video format and mobile applications. We decided to delve deeper into the topic and conduct an additional survey, expanding the sample size to 279 respondents. The respondents were selected in three schools in the city of Tashkent, among students in grades 7, 8 and 9. The distribution of pupils by schools and classes was even, by gender, pupils were distributed as follows: boys - 53.0%, girls - 47.0%.

The data were collected using a questionnaire method. The representativeness of the study on the scale of the studied group is ensured by the use of a multi-stage stratified sample, with a ten percent error, at a reliability level of 95%. As the main

criteria of the survey, we chose a number of questions showing the interest of students in literature lessons, in particular to the question "Are you interested in the subject of literature?", 42.7% of survey participants answered yes, 29.0% reported an average level of interest, and 21.9% of respondents reported that they were not interested in literature lessons. After the method of cross-frequency analysis, we decided to find out the trends in these answers among those selected for socio-demographic indicators.

The results of survey show that, in general, literature lessons at school are more engrossing for girls, while boys showed an average level of interest to a greater extent (tab. 1)

Table 1

Distribution of answers to the question "Are you interested in the subject of literature?" by gender of respondents

	Yes	No	Average
Male	0,28	0,20	0,52
Female	0,60	0,24	0,17
Total	0,43	0,22	0,35

This distribution can be considered statistically significant at the level of 10% error for the studied groups. What is more, to test the hypothesis about the influence of the teacher and the bias of the school itself in the field of conducting literature classes, we carried out another cross-frequency analysis, according to the class of students (Table 2).

Table 2

Distribution of answers to the question "Are you interested in the subject of literature?" by class of respondents

	Yes	No	Average
7th grade	0,20	0,39	0,41
8th grade	0,53	0,13	0,34
9th grade	0,55	0,14	0,31
Total	0,43	0,22	0,35

The results show us that, to a large extent, the manifestation of interest in literature classes also depends on the teacher and the attention that the school pays to this subject. Next, we examined the overall student satisfaction with literature lessons in terms of textbook design and visual design. Thus, the majority of survey participants (60.9%) reported that they were not satisfied with the design of the available literature textbooks. To the question "Are there pictures in the textbook of the heroes of the artwork being studied?" - 81.4% answered no. Moreover, the vast majority of respondents noted that textbooks are not accompanied by additional audio and video materials. Probably, the factors described above also caused the general self-assessment of the assimilation of theoretical knowledge by students, of which only 13.6% reported that they were fully able to assimilate theoretical material.

Discussion.

Science and evolution are constantly altering. Initially, the education system was tasked with educating a comprehensively developed generation. Later this task was replaced by providing a good education and a career. However, over the past period, both have come under fire. Today's students are required to be creative, to strive to change the knowledge that they have acquired, and to constantly master the achievements of science (2, 2010). In this sense, it is vital to constantly update the textbooks and manuals that define the content of literary education on the basis of

scientific progress and changes in society. Woefully, most of the existing textbooks do not meet the methodological requirements. Researchers Andy Smart and Shanti Jagannat have studied the policy of creating and publishing textbooks in Asian countries, noting that a carefully designed textbook is not a limitation for the teacher, but the closest assistant that saves his energy and time (3, 2018). In addition, the textbook is a mandatory tool for working with pupils and teaching the literary material being studied. Indeed, the textbook - school pedagogy - is one of the key factors determining the level of quality of education, in which the educational outcome is interrelated and at the same time interdependent (4, 2011). Besides, in recent years, although a lot of research has been done to improve the competence of teachers, the implementation of new interactive methods, the main factor that ensures the effectiveness of education - textbooks - is ignored (5, 2010). According to research conducted by international organizations, only half of students are able to put into practice the knowledge they have acquired.

The analysis of textbooks shows the need to further improve the methodological system of teaching folk epics, which are large in size and have several options, based on modern requirements. Consequently, textbooks need to be updated to nurture young people who are able to think independently and realize their intellectual and creative potential, and to transition to a competent approach to education (6, 2015).

The fact that the data in some textbooks are outdated from a scientific point of view, the information is inconsistent, and the lack of methodological guidelines for the teacher in most textbooks also causes a lot of misunderstanding. Most of the literature textbooks have been reprinted. They have been published at least four times. Some even up to 7 times. The surnames of some authors are enclosed in a rectangular frame. It is surprising that textbooks are being rewritten and published on behalf of the deceased.

Admittedly, among the existing new textbooks and manuals, enriched scientifically and methodologically, there are textbooks that do not meet today's

requirements, didactic methods that do not justify themselves, which lead to a sharp decline in the effectiveness of literary education. As a matter of course, the teacher can not only rely on the textbook, but also use a number of materials on the topic, recommending students to read additional literature on the topic covered. However, the teacher may not have the time, energy, desire, or experience to search or create teaching materials other than the textbook. It should be taken into consideration that families in need of social protection will not be able to purchase resources other than textbooks. In addition, the student does not study only "Literature" at school. It is advisable that the study load should correspond to pupils' age and level of mastery.

Conclusion.

Textbooks are a mirror that reflects the strengths and weaknesses of each state's education system. This is why a comparative study and analysis of textbooks from schools around the world is essential. It is impossible to learn the spirit of science from a textbook or article. They may be able to teach us physics and chemistry and many other disciplines at university, but it is up to us to develop a gut feeling for how best to do science. Experiments have shown that it is needed to create modern, thorough and perfect new generation textbooks. Notwithstanding, textbooks alone cannot be a ready-made solution in ensuring lesson effectiveness. The main value in literary education is a teacher, of course. But the fact that not all teachers are equally creative and enterprising requires careful and perfect creation of textbooks.

At school, the student is required to master not the works of the author that he likes or wishes, but all the topics included in the textbook in accordance with the curriculum. Textbooks created in accordance with modern requirements play an important role in making compulsory lessons fascinating. Designed in an attractive, methodologically sound way, the textbooks not only make the lessons interesting and effective, but also ensure that students actively participate in the lesson and master the subject in depth.

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